

Piotr Wojtal - Jarosław Wilczyński - Nina Kowalik (Eds)

4th Conference World of Gravettian Hunters

Kraków, Poland, 20 - 24 May 2024

Abstracts

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ISEA PAS

2024

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THURSDAY 23.05.2019**Session 10:00 – 14:00****(15 minutes presentation + 5 minutes discussion)****Chairman: Susanne C. Münzel**

- 10:00 **Vitaly I. Usyk, Roman Garba, Natalia Gerasimenko, Larissa Kulakovska, Freddy Damblon, Philip R.Nigst** – Searching for the Gravettian along the Northeastern Fringes of the Pannonian Plain: The upper cultural layers of Korolevo II, Ukraine
- 10:20 **Timothée Libois** – The Gravettian site of Mezhygirtsy I (Ukraine): A contextual and technological reassessment
- 10:40 **Bogdan Ridush, Yana Popiuk, Olesia Kononenko, Vasyl Shavransky, Mykola Ilkiv** – The traces of Upper Palaeolithic hunters on the Upper Prut
- 11:00 **Pavlo Shydlovskiy, Diana Dudnyk, Ostap Tsvirkun, Marharyta Chymyrys** – Structure of Epigravettian Dwellings: The Mezhyrich Fourth Dwelling Case Study
- 11:20 **Laëtitia Demay, Theodor Obadã, Sergei Covalenco, Roman Croitor, Viorica Pascari, Afanasie Prepelita, Marie–Anne Julien, Antoine Zazzo, Olivier Tombret, Xavier Gallet, Matthieu Lebon, Stéphane Péan** – Human occupations in the Carpathian–Dniester area during the Last Glacial Maximum: new investigations in Republic of Moldova
- 11:40 **Diana Dudnyk** – The core reduction strategies of the Epigravettian industries of the Mid Dnipro basin
- 11:50 Discussion

*12:20 Coffee break***Poster session 12:50 – 14:00****(5 minutes presentation + 5 minutes discussion)**

- 12:50 **Dorothee G. Drucker, Mahym Amanova, Federica Fontana** – Isotopic tracking of the ecology of red deer during the Late Glacial in the south–eastern Alps: evidence from Riparo Tagliente (Verona, Italy)

Structure of Epigravettian Dwellings: The Mezhyrich Fourth Dwelling Case Study

Pavlo SHYDLOVSKYI¹, Diana DUDNYK², Ostap TSVIRKUN³,
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The Mezhyrich Epigravettian settlement is primarily renowned for its residential structures constructed with mammoth bones. Initial excavations conducted between 1966 and 1974 by I. Pidoplichko explored three residential units, yielding materials that are well-documented in scientific literature. Dwelling 4, unearthed in 1976 and partially investigated by M. Gladkikh, N. Kornietz, and O. Soffer, was left *in situ* for future preservation and comprehensive research.

From 2018 to 2023, research on Dwelling 4 resumed, meticulously documenting all discovered materials and layers. Despite the ongoing war, this structure is the sole Upper Palaeolithic residential site in Ukraine subject to regular investigation using modern field study methods. The outcome of this research includes the identification of numerous artefacts and a clearer understanding of the dwelling's structural features.

The structure itself is an oval, approximately 6 m in diameter, constructed from large mammoth bones. The foundation consists of regularly arranged mammoth skulls, occasionally supplemented by large long bones. The outer circle, or lining, is composed of flat bones such as scapulae and pelvises. The entrance, located to the south, is distinguished by the presence of large tusks fallen inside the structure and a „fence” made of sub-vertically installed long bones. There is a noticeable ashy area in the centre indicating the presence of an inner hearth. Modern radiocarbon dating of mid-mammal bones places the structure between 14,800 and 14,600 BP, corresponding to 18,239–17,596 calBP.

Modern research is conducted in two opposing areas relative to the central hearth: the West and East sections. Stratigraphic observations reveal multiple layers (at least three), representing former living surfaces within the dwelling. The horizontal distribution of

findings suggests the presence of various functionally distinct areas within the living space. On the East section, the „Workshop” feature was discovered, comprising two clusters of flint products situated on different levels. The first cluster was positioned near the mammoth skull forming the dwelling’s base (2nd, middle horizon). The second cluster (3rd, lower horizon), was covered by a series of processed mammoth ribs and a fragment of a processed tusk. Nearby, a young mammoth scapula with ochre traces on its surface was found. The lithic assemblage, totalling 1,070 items, primarily consists of production waste - lamellar products, flakes, and chips, along with individual cores and tools. In the West section, opposite the hearth, anatomical groups of medium-sized mammals and a series of bone products related to leather processing — needles and awls — were discovered in the 2nd, middle horizon. The lower, 3rd layer (?) of this area is characterized by a significant saturation of ochre and the presence of stone grinders.

Analysis of the spatial distribution of flint products in other Mezhyrich dwellings has validated a comparable organizational system of internal objects. Specifically, when the entrance to the dwelling was positioned in the southern part, concentrations of flint products were observed in the eastern parts of the internal fillings of Dwellings 1 and 2. Such an arrangement of the internal space may indicate a single pattern of behaviour among the population of the Epigravettian Mezhyrich type in the Middle Dnipro area.